

STUDY ON PREPARATION AND FLAME RETARDANT PROPERTIES OF EPOXY/GRAPHENE OXIDE NANOSHEETS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy is extensively used in everyday life, in coatings, semiconductor packaging, electrical equipment, insulation and adhesives. Since epoxy has very favorable mechanical properties and low shrinkage characteristics when cured, it has attracted much interest. However, since it is flammable, its development has been limited by its flammability.

The flame retardant containing silicon and phosphorus was grafted onto the surface of graphene oxide nanosheets (GON) via a condensation reaction. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy verifies that flame retardant did not only covalently bond to GON as a functionalization moiety, but partly restored its conjugated structure as a reducing agent. The flame retardant on graphene sheets oxide was observed by transmission electron microscopy.

The flame retardancy and thermal stability of epoxy/functionalized GON (f-GON) nanocomposites that contain various weight fractions of f-GON were studied using the limiting oxygen index test, UL-94 test and by thermogravimetric analysis in nitrogen. The composites containing 10 wt% f-GON can pass V-0 rating in UL-94 test. Adding 10 wt % f-GON in epoxy greatly increased the char yield and LOI by 42% and 80%, respectively. Epoxy/f-GON nanocomposites with phosphorus, silicon and graphene layer structures were found to exhibit much greater flame retardancy than neat epoxy. The synergistic effects among silicon, phosphorus and GON can improve the flame retardancy of epoxy resin.

The phosphorus, silicon and GON layer structures of DPPES-GNO caused the continuous and insulating char layer to protect the inner polymer matrix. The approach that is described herein has great potential for the development of a novel synergistic phosphorus/silicon-graphene nanosheets oxide flame-retardant with polymer nanocomposite applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy is extensively used in everyday life, in coatings, semiconductor packaging, electrical equipment, insulation and adhesives. Since epoxy has very favorable mechanical properties and low shrinkage characteristics when cured, it has attracted much interest. However, since it is flammable, its development has been limited by its flammability. In recent years, various scholars have been involved in developing flame retardants [1-4]. This work develops a new flame-retardant for epoxy resin.

In this work, a flame retardant that contained silicon and phosphorus was grafted onto graphene oxide nanosheet (GON), and then added to epoxy resin to form a composite. The thermal and flame retardant properties of the composites were examined by thermogravimetry and determination of the limiting oxygen index.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Graphene nanosheets (Knano Graphene Technology Corporation Limited, Xiamen, China) were utilized as the starting material for the preparation of graphene nanosheets oxide. The graphene nanosheets had a thickness of 5-15 nm, a purity of 99.5%, and a density of 2.25 g/cm³. 2-(Diphenylphosphino)ethyltriethoxy silane (DPPES, 92% pure) was purchased from Acros Chemical Co, New Jersey, USA. Diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM) was purchased from TCI Chemical Co, Tokyo, Japan. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 180 g eq⁻¹ was obtained from Nan Ya Plastics Corporation, Taipei, Taiwan. Anhydrous stabilized tetrahydrofuran (THF) was obtained from Lancaster Co., Morecambe, Lancashire, U.K.

2.2 Preparation of graphene oxide nanosheet (GON)

Graphene nanosheets (GNs) powder was oxidized by the improved method for synthesizing graphene oxide [5]. First, graphite (3g) was mixed with a 9 : 1 mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄/H₃PO₄ (360 : 40 mL) and KMnO₄ (18g) in a flask that was kept in an ice bath. The mixture was stirred for 12 h. The reaction mixture was remained cool and poured onto ice (~400 mL) with 30% H₂O₂ (3 mL). The filtrate was centrifuged (6000 rpm for 10 min) and the supernatant was decanted away. The remaining solid material was then washed in 200 mL of water, 200 mL of 30% HCl, and 200 mL of ethanol twice in that order; for each wash, the mixture was centrifuged (6000 rpm for 4 h), and the supernatant was decanted away. The material that remained after this extended, multiple-wash process was coagulated using 200 mL of ether, and the resulting suspension was filtered over a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) membrane with a pore size of 0.45 μm. The GON that was obtained on the filter was vacuum-dried overnight at room temperature. (Scheme 1 (a))

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication of (a) GNO and (b) DPPES-GNO.

2.3 Synthesis of functionalized graphene oxide nanosheets

The as-prepared 1g GON was first suspended in 200 mL THF and then 1g DPPES was added into the solution. It was dispersed for 30 min in an ultrasonic bath. Then, the suspension was transferred into a three-neck flask prepared with N₂. Then, another THF solution (50 mL) of hydrochloric acid and deionized water (0.05 : 4 molar ratio) was added with stirring. The mixture was heated to 80°C and refluxed for 12 h under N₂. After the functionalization process had been completed, the mixture was separated by filtration through a 0.2 μm PTFE membrane and thoroughly washed using anhydrous

THF and acetone to remove the residual DPPES. It was then dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C overnight to remove the solvent. (Scheme 1 (b))

2.4 Preparation of epoxy/DPPES-GON nanocomposites

Various amounts of DPPES-GON were added to acetone and stirred until DPPES-GON had completely dispersed to form a black solution. Then, the DPPES-GON solutions were separately added to the epoxy resin and stirred until homogeneous mixtures were obtained. DDM was used as a hardener. The reactants were mixed in a stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 0.5 (epoxy resin/DDM) with constant stirring until the solutions were completely homogeneous. These mixtures were heated in a vacuum oven at approximately 80 °C to remove excess solvent. Then, the samples were cured at 120, 140 and 160 °C for 3 h and post-cured at 180 °C for 2 h. Finally, the samples were allowed to cool slowly to room temperature, and yielding epoxy/DPPES-GON nanocomposites. For comparison, pristine Epoxy/GON nanocomposites with various GON contents were also prepared under similar processing conditions.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 FTIR of GON and DPPES-GON

Figure 1 displays FT-IR spectra of GON and DPPES-GON. In the spectrum of GON, the broad band at 3600~3400cm⁻¹ is attributed to the stretching of the -OH groups on the GON surface, while the band at 1740 cm⁻¹ is associated with the stretching of the C=O bond in carboxylic groups. The peaks at 1368 cm⁻¹ and 1214 cm⁻¹ arose from the bending of -OH and the epoxide group stretching of the C-O-C bond. The absorption peak at 1634 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the skeletal vibration of unoxidized graphitic domains [6-9]. The peaks at wavenumbers 2980 cm⁻¹, 1593 cm⁻¹ and 952 cm⁻¹ are the characteristic peaks of C-H, a phenyl group and the Si-O groups in DPPES, respectively [10-12].

The peaks associated with -CH, -CH₂ (3000~2800 cm⁻¹), phenyl (1637 cm⁻¹), P-CH₂ (1420 cm⁻¹), Si-O-C (1225 cm⁻¹), Si-O-Si (1097 cm⁻¹) and Si-OH (900 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of DPPES-GON indicate the successful grafting reaction of DPPES on GON surfaces in Figure 1.

Figure 1 FT-IR spectra of GNO and DPPES-GNO

3.2 Morphology of GON and DPPES-GON

In order to obtain the morphological information of GON and DPPES-GON, TEM observations are conducted. Figure 2 displays the TEM images of (a) GON and (b) DPPES-GON. TEM analysis demonstrates that GON sheets on the top of a copper grid (Fig. 2(a)) typically comprise flat yet wrinkled nanoplatelets with diameters of several hundred nanometers but, after surface functionalization, they appear to dark following the grafting of DPPES (Fig. 2(b)).

Figure 2 TEM images of (a) GNO (b) DPPES-GNO

3.3 Thermal properties of epoxy/DPPES-GON composites

The thermal stabilities of these composites were determined by thermal gravimetric analysis. Figures 3 and 4 and Table 1 present TGA and DTG of epoxy composites with various DPPES-GON and GON contents, respectively, that were heated at a rate of 10 °C/min under N₂. Td₅ is the temperature when the weight loss of the sample reaches its 5%. Figure 3 and Table 1 indicate that the Td₅s of DPPES-GON nanocomposites were lower than that of pure epoxy resin, because the DPPES moiety contains a phosphorous functional group that may be degraded at a relatively low temperature, promoting char formation. The Si–O–Si segments formed thermally stable silica compounds. Due to that silicon has lower surface energy, silica may migrate to the char surface and therefore form a protective layer that retards further degradation of the char at higher temperatures [11, 13-17]. GON contain more oxygen-containing groups than DPPES-GON. Greater mass loss for epoxy/GON 10% occurred around 180-300 °C, which was due to the removal of oxygen-containing groups of GON [13, 18]. Compared with epoxy/GON 10% composite from figure 3, the epoxy/DPPES-GON 10% composites has higher char yield at the same filler loading from room temperature to 800 °C, suggesting epoxy/DPPES-GON composite has better thermal stability than that of epoxy/GON composites. The char yield of DPPES-GON nanocomposites increased with DPPES-GON content, indicating that the composites were thermally stable at high temperature. Rongjie Yang [19] research team had reported that the formation of a -P(=O)-O-Si- structure increases both the quantity and the thermal stability of the char in the condensed phase. Yuan Hu [20] showed that the presence of graphene exhibited superior thermal-oxidative resistance of the char layer compared to the composite containing silicon, which effectively retarded the mass and heat transfer between the flame and the burning substrate, thus the heat release rate and total heat release of the flame retardant composites containing graphene was significantly reduced during combustion.

Figure 3 TGA thermograms of epoxy composites with various DPPES-GNO and GNO contents (wt%).

Figure 4 DTG of Epoxy resin with various DPPES-GNO and GNO contents (wt%)

Sample	T _{d5} ^a (°C)	T _{max} ^b (wt%/ °C)	Char residue (wt%) at 800°C	IPDT ^c (°C)	UL- 94
Neat Epoxy	383	-29.2	14.9	634	Fail
Epoxy/DPPES-GON 1%	381	-25.1	15.7	659	Fail
Epoxy/DPPES-GON 5%	375	-24.0	19.1	723	Fail
Epoxy/DPPES-GON 10%	277	-19.1	25.6	843	V-0
Epoxy/DPPES 10%	391	-12.4	14.3	675	Fail
Epoxy/GON 10%	209	-21.5	21.2	750	Fail

^aT_{d5} is the temperature when the weight loss of the sample reaches its 5%.

^bT_{max} is the temperature when the weight loss of the sample reaches its maximum.

^cThe integral procedural decomposition temperature (IPDT) takes into account the whole degradation process.

Table 1 Selected Results of TGA Testing

The DTG curves in Fig. 4 and Table 1 demonstrate that the composites had a lower weight loss rate than pure epoxy. The increase in the rate of mass loss with temperature for the DPPES-GON

composites was significantly lower than that for pure epoxy, and the former formed more residue, revealing that the thermal stability of DPPES-GON was significantly better than that of epoxy-amine crosslinked thermoset. Figure 10 showed that the rate of weight loss for DPPES-GON composites decreases with the increasing of the contents of DPPES-GON fillers. The temperatures (T_m) at which the first derivatives of the weight loss curves of the composites are maximal mass loss rate exceeded that of pure epoxy, revealing that DPPES-GON enhances the thermal stability of the polymer matrix and retards the pyrolysis of resin. This increase in thermal stability may be caused by the thermal barrier effect of the GON layers structure and from the interactions between epoxy and DPPES-GON. The DPPES-GON layers have a shielding effect and reduce the rate of decomposition of the composite. The thermal stability of DPPES-GON composites is concluded to increase with DPPES-GON content, owing to the excellent thermal stability of DPPES-GON. The thermal stability of epoxy/DPPES-GON composites exceeds that of epoxy/GON composites from 400 to 800 °C, perhaps because the change in the compatibility between the polymers and GON at their interfaces improves the heat-resistant performance of epoxy/DPPES-GON composites.

The integral procedure decomposition temperature (IPDT) that was proposed by Doyle [21] concerns the volatile parts of the polymeric materials and is used to estimate their inherent thermal stability [22-23]. From Table 1, the IPDT of pure epoxy was 634 °C and the IPDTs of the composites exceeded that of pure epoxy. Inorganic components improve the thermal stability of pure epoxy.

3.4 Flame retardancy

UL-94 is a vertical burning test method for flame retardancy, which contains three rating, V-0, V-1 and V-2. The flame retardancy properties is V-0 > V-1 > V-2. UL-94 testing results of the composites are presented in Table 1. The results, obtained from UL-94 V test, show that neat epoxy pass UL-94 V rating from fail to V-0 rating by addition of DPPES-GON at the highest concentration, namely 10 wt%. The epoxy/DPPES 10% and epoxy/GON 10% composites cannot pass the UL-94 testing. Figure 5 presents the LOI values of GON and DPPES-GON/epoxy nanocomposites. The LOI value of GON/epoxy nanocomposite increased with DPPES-GON content. However, it exceeded that of the neat epoxy system which is only 20 %. The flame retardancy of DPPES-GON/epoxy nanocomposites increased with DPPES-GON content. The LOI values of DPPES-GON/epoxy nanocomposites improved significantly from 20% to 36% as the DPPES-GON content was increased from 0 to 10 wt %. This finding is consistent with the results concerning char yield. It has been reported that high char yields and larger LOI values are indicative of better flame-retardant properties in corresponding references [24-25]. Together, these results show that DPPES-GON imparts strong flame-retardancy to epoxy resin at low filler loadings. Figure 5 and Table 1 present that the LOI value of DPPES-GON 10 wt% composites is higher than that of DPPES 10 wt% composite or GON 10 wt% composite alone at the same filler loading, revealing that the synergistic effects of silicon, phosphorus and graphene nanosheets oxide. Camino et al. [26-27] reported that the thermal degradation of the compounds containing phosphorus lead to the formation of H_3PO_4 and consequently pyrophosphoric acid. The residue from the condensation of phosphoric acid played the main role in combustion. Glass-like phosphorus-containing solid residue is formed from the condensation of pyrophosphoric acid, this layer would limit the production of combustible gases and inhibit the combustion process. Silicon also plays an important role in this flame retardant system. The mechanism of flame retardancy of a silicon-containing material is related to the low surface energy of silicon, which moves to the surface to as a protective layer. The protective char layer is evidenced by the char that is obtained from the samples following the LOI test. In this work, the protective layer held back the flammable gases and isolated the heat from the unburned matrix. As the sample was burned further, the silicon moved to the surface as a protective layer owing to its low surface energy. The silicon-containing compounds increased the high-temperature thermal stability because their oxidized products were silicon dioxide, which protected the layer [28]. The origin of the flame-retarding behavior of GON is thought to be its formation of a continuous, protective char layer that acts as a thermal insulator and a mass transport barrier [29-32]. Clearly, the synergistic effects of silicon, phosphorus and graphene nanosheets oxide improve the flame retardancy of epoxy resin.

Figure 5 LOI of Epoxy composites with various DPPES-GNO and GNO contents (wt%)

4 CONCLUSIONS

DPPES was grafted onto the surface of GNO by condensation to form a synergistic phosphorus/silicon-containing GNO flame retardant (DPPES-GNO). A series of nanocomposites that contained 0, 1, 5, and 10 wt % DPPES-GNO were prepared. XPS, FTIR, Raman spectroscopy and TEM verified that DPPES covalently bonded to GNO. Furthermore, the addition of DPPES-GNO (up to 10 wt %) to neat epoxy significantly increased its thermal stability, improved the char yield and LOI by 42% and 80%, respectively. The phosphorus, silicon and GNO layer structures of DPPES-GNO caused the continuous and insulating char layer to protect the inner polymer matrix. The approach that is described herein has great potential for the development of a novel synergistic phosphorus/silicon-graphene nanosheets oxide flame-retardant with polymer nanocomposite applications.

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